

The effect of hospital competition on the quality of care

Authors: *Sara Jamalabadi and Luigi Siciliani*

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Based on the theory, when prices are set administratively, competition among hospitals fosters quality competition and thereby improves the quality of care. However, little empirical evidence exists on the effect of competition on quality of care. Additionally, empirical evidence from Germany is missing so far. This study aims to identify the effect of hospital competition on the quality of care in Germany.

Study Design: We employ two datasets in our analysis. We obtain the patient records treated with drug-eluting stents following Acute Myocardial Infarction (AMI) from a large German sickness fund from 2014-2017. We obtain the hospital characteristics from German hospital quality reports. We use a distance-weighted method to calculate the competition each hospital faces, which assigns weights by number of AMI admissions and inversely by distance so that distant hospitals have less importance relative to close hospitals but may still have an effect. Quality of care is assessed based on in-hospital mortality and 30-days, 6-month, one-year, and two-year post-discharge mortality and readmission.

We use a logit model accounting for patient characteristics such as age, gender, comorbidities, being an emergency admission and transferred from another hospital, hospital characteristics such as being a university hospital and high volume hospital, and we control for the distance to the hospital to estimate the probability of mortality and readmission by market competitiveness.

Results: Our analysis includes 33,089 records. The mean in-hospital mortality rate is 0.045. Patients treated in hospitals in low competition markets are 28% more likely to survive than the patients treated in hospitals in high competition markets ($p < 0.01$). Similarly, patients treated in high competition markets are more likely to be readmitted than the patients treated in low competition markets even though the difference is not statistically significant. The results are robust when the Herfindahl–Hirschman Index of hospitals within a 20 km radius is used to measure the competitiveness of the markets.

Conclusions: Our results are notably in contrast with most results from the UK and the US, which suggests that competition is an essential mechanism for enhancing the quality of care patients receive. High hospital competition does not have a positive effect on the quality of care for patients treated with drug-eluting stents following AMI in Germany. Therefore, the effect of competition on quality of care may be highly context-dependent, and policymakers should pay attention to the context (e.g., Germany vs. the US) when they consider reform on competition in healthcare.